

Adaptation of Traditional Tavern Culture to New Generation Taverns, Loyalty, and the Impact of Social Benefit: The Case of Çanakkale

Bahattin Hamarat / Lect.

Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Faculty of Tourism, Department of Tourism Management
bhamarat@comu.edu.tr

Lokman Güzel / Ph.D. Candidate

Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Faculty of Tourism, Department of Tourism Management
lkmn.gzll@gmail.com

Mutlu Can* / Ph.D. Candidate

Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Faculty of Tourism, Department of Tourism Management
cm.mutlucan@gmail.com

Erol Duran / Prof. Dr.

Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Faculty of Tourism, Department of Tourism Management
erolduran@comu.edu.tr

Nur Undey / Assoc. Prof. Dr.

2N1K Consulting Services, Founding Member
nurkalpak@gmail.com

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

Traditional taverns have endured as significant cultural assets of Anatolian lands. However, changes in consumption habits have led to the emergence of new-generation taverns. This shift has resulted in the neglect of traditional taverns, which are an important component of cultural heritage. This study focuses on traditional taverns and their patrons within the scope of intangible cultural heritage. It investigates the effects of individuals' perceptions of traditional tavern culture, loyalty to traditional taverns, and perceptions of social benefit on their adaptation to new generation taverns. The research was conducted with individuals in Çanakkale who embrace traditional tavern culture. Data were collected from 409 regular patrons of traditional taverns in Çanakkale using face-to-face and online survey techniques. Relationships among the latent variables were analyzed through structural equation modeling (SEM). The findings indicate that traditional tavern culture positively influences loyalty and social benefit. Similarly, individuals' perceptions of social

benefit regarding traditional taverns were found to increase loyalty, yet showed no significant effect on adaptation to new generation taverns. Moreover, as individuals' traditional tavern culture strengthens, their adaptation to new generation taverns decreases. Likewise, higher loyalty to traditional taverns corresponds to lower adaptation to new generation taverns. Additionally, as individuals age, their adaptation to new generation taverns declines. However, no significant relationship was found between traditional tavern experience and adaptation to new generation taverns. These results highlight the role of traditional tavern culture in preserving cultural heritage and its implications for understanding changing consumption patterns in the hospitality sector.

Keywords: Traditional Tavern, New Generation Tavern, Social Benefit, Loyalty, Intangible Cultural Heritage, Structural Equation Model.

JEL Codes: L82, L83, M14

Citation: Hamarat, B., Güzel, L., Can, M., Duran, E., & Ündey, N. (2025). Adaptation of traditional tavern culture to new generation taverns, loyalty, and the impact of social benefit: The case of Çanakkale. *Researches on Multidisciplinary Approaches (ROMAYA Journal)*, 5(2), 387–403.

1. Introduction

Human beings are inherently social creatures (Işık, 2018). Eating and drinking are fundamental activities that fulfill our biological needs (Ay & Şahin 2014). While this basic phenomenon is realized, people can interact with different cultures by engaging in social communications. Each society has its own cultural elements. Social communications can occur when different cultures experience joy, grief and entertainment activities together (Ciğerim, 2001; Erdem et al., 2018). While this basic phenomenon is realized, people can interact with different cultures by engaging in social communications. Each society has its own cultural elements. Social communications can occur when different cultures experience joy, grief and entertainment activities together (Ciğerim, 2001; Erdem et al., 2018).

These places, which have been one of the fundamental values that form the cultural structures of societies, are one of the most important cultural elements that include the geographical lifestyles, production styles, historical development processes, economic and cultural activities, beliefs and ethnic characteristics of societies (Üçer & Peşken 2001, Ciğerim, 2001; Erdem et al., 2018). Taverns, have been the examples of Anatolia's food and beverage culture which survived to this day were founded on the basis of social communications and interaction. However, due to the developments of technology and tourism, it has undergone changes in order to maintain its existence as cultural heritage.

The industrial revolution and the intensification of technological developments have caused people's leisure times to increase and their understanding of entertainment to change. The changing consumption behavior had caused an increase in product diversity and competition in the emerging market. In this context, businesses have tended to develop new trends and innovations in order to keep up with this change and respond to consumer demands (Tariñç & Özbek, 2022). The industrial revolution and the intensification of technological developments have caused people's leisure times to increase and their understanding of entertainment to change. The changing consumption behavior had caused an increase in product diversity and competition in the emerging market. In this context, businesses have tended to develop new trends and innovations in order to keep up with this change and respond to consumer demands (Tariñç & Özbek, 2022). These newly developed trends and innovations can cause traditional cultures to degenerate and change. Especially the young generations' excessive contact with technology may cause them moving away from their culture and prevent transmitting it to the next generation. This can cause cultural changes and disruptions (Seylan and Güney, 2014)

Cultural changes and corruption have been also expressed as the degeneration and destruction of religion, language, morality, traditions and customs (Şahin, 2011). Accordingly, the unique eating and drinking culture of the society has been also changing. Food, food types, beverages, and the need for eating and drinking that nourish the society, and the places, beliefs and practices formed in this context have been defined as a holistic and unique cultural structure (Maviş, 2008; Mankan and Özçelik, 2019; Güler, 2010). Based on this definition, it is possible to emphasize that there is a significantly strong bond between culture and the concept of food and beverage (Sormaz & Kaya, 2019).

In the literature, it is seen that there are studies that deal with traditional taverns from different perspectives. Erdinçli (2023) examined the taverns that existed from the 16 th century to the 20 th century. Altun & Elidemir (2023) examined the products in the kitchen of the meyhanes in Cyprus from a gastronomic point of view. Yalap (2017) emphasized the importance of taverns as the subject of poems in Turkish literature. Yenici (2020) emphasized the importance of tavern culture by examining the photographs of the famous photographer Ara Güler reflecting the tavern culture. Çapraz (2018) states that taverns are home to the basis of the minstrel rivalries in Turkish culture and that they are performed in taverns. In this direction, it is obvious that taverns have made many contributions to Turkish literature. In the literature, it is seen that taverns have social benefits, but they are not directly analyzed in terms of social benefit. This situation reveals the originality of the study. Examining the traditional tavern patrons by addressing the concept of loyalty in the context of place-human relationship supports the originality of the study.

In the research, the transformation of traditional taverns into new generation taverns, focusing on how social benefits, traditional tavern culture, and loyalty influence adaptation to these new spaces. It also investigates whether age and years of tavern-going experience affect adaptation. Considering the impact of technology on consumption habits and spatial preferences, the study explores the role of taverns as intangible cultural heritage, particularly their contribution to social benefits and loyalty in human-space relations. Since no existing model analyzes the factors influencing adaptation to new generation taverns, this research is expected to fill a gap and contribute to the literature.

1.1. Traditional and New Generation Tavern

Traditional taverns have survived from the Ottoman period to the present day and stand out as an element that reflects the food and beverage culture of

Adaptation of Traditional Tavern Culture to New Generation Taverns, Loyalty, and the Impact of Social Benefit: The Case of Çanakkale

Anatolia. Taverns have been defined as social places where people come together to eat, rest and spend time. Taverns were places that served food and beverages and generally run by non-Muslims during the Ottoman period. With the proclamation of the Republic, taverns have been opened in many places as a result of the Anatolian people's adaptation to the tavern culture. The concept of taverns, generally associated with maritime and maritime trade, continues to exist in the coastal cities of Anatolia (Açhan, 2018; Erdiñçli, 2020b; Şimşek, 2021).

When considered historically, traditional taverns have been known as places where those engaged in maritime activities and maritime trade visited ports to spend time in the Byzantine period (Öztekin, 2005) The port culture, which was formed by different nations coming together at that time, has been observed in historical sources that has survived to the present day as taverns. When historical sources have been examined, it is seen that in the port culture, various drinks were consumed in the places located in the ports and various appetizers were served to accompany the drinks (Erdiñçli, 2023). Today, the same service continues in taverns.

These food and beverage venues, which have survived from the Byzantine period to the present day, have become a culture that reflects and pioneers the gastronomy of Anatolia (Öncü et al., 2001). With the change in technology and people's consumption understanding, traditional taverns have undergone changes and deteriorations in order to survive in their market. Today, it has still referred as a culture that continues to exist traditionally and is kept alive in many provinces, especially İstanbul (Erdiñçli, 2020b).

New generation taverns have been places that bring a modern and contemporary (popular) interpretation to traditional tavern customs and culture. These types of taverns do not preserve the traditional elements that have been refined through historical accumulation, and offer different atmospheres with contemporary gastronomy, modern design, creative appetizers and food menus (Yıldız & Davutođlu, 2020; Güzel et al., 2023). They differ from traditional taverns from their decoration to their lighting. New generation taverns have been venues that stand out with their entertainment-centered stage shows (Aydın, 2022). In these places, deep relationships are not established; they create environments that are superficial and far from emotional connections. In this sense, new generation taverns are modern places that emphasize consumption and are places that express lighter, flexible relationships (Demiral & Özel, 2016; Şahin & Yaziciođlu, 2020).

The social development of the world and the involvement of women in business life in Anatolia have caused the eating and drinking habits of individuals in Anatolia to change (Pine & Gilmore, 1999). Espe-

cially with the declaration of the Republic, the increase in women's social rights and their presence in business life have led to some changes in Anatolian culture. These changes can be considered as the pioneers of the change in Turkish gastronomy. In this context, the social benefit-creating feature of traditional taverns and the loyalty-creating feature, which has been identified with the concept of loyalty-regularity within the framework of this benefit, stand out as concepts that need to be addressed separately. These concepts are also important in terms of their positive reflections on tourism.

1.2. Social Benefit

The tourism sector has become an important sector in the world economy in the last century. It has become a locomotive sector that provides an important source of commercial income for countries (Köşker, 2024). The tourism sector is linked to many sectors. Its impact on more than one sector can play an important role in the development of the country. Many studies in the literature emphasize that tourism activities improve community life and the quality of social life (Besculides et al., 2002; Attanasi et al., 2013; Yolal et al., 2016). Tourism activities such as cultural travel contribute to social benefits (Yolal, 2017).

Social benefits can be listed as follows: increase in income level, increase in tax revenues, positive increases in employment, diversification of economic inputs, enrichment in social, cultural and environmental factors (Andereck et al., 2005; Duman et al., 2021). The realization of touristic activities helps to increase public services in cities, urban structuring, strengthening the infrastructure and increasing investments in terms of social benefits (Zhuang et al., 2019; Eryer, 2024).

Developments in the field of tourism can affect local people in many ways in terms of social benefits. These include the protection of local values, tolerance, foreign language learning, cultural mobilization, information exchange, awareness about the protection of historical and cultural assets, and the protection of cultural resources (Uygur & Baykan, 2007; Kozak et al., 2013).

Protecting traditional taverns within the scope of intangible cultural heritage is likely to help preserve Anatolian gastronomy culture. Preserving tavern culture and gastronomy and ensuring its survival through incentives can help cities' food and beverage cultures come to the fore and become centers of attraction (Deniz, 2024).

As traditional taverns have been one of the basic inputs of Anatolian culture can enable the preservation of social identity in the destination they are located. Presenting the cultural values of the taverns and reflect this culture to tourists will strengthen the

ties between society and increase awareness of social identity, social loyalty and cultural values. Touristic activities such as cultural travels contribute to social benefit (Yolal, 2017). Thus, traditional taverns will remain as places that best reflect the cultural identity, cultural structure and eating- drinking rituals (Kayran & Atçı, 2024; Sezen & Külekçi, 2020).

Traditional taverns have been one of the most basic elements of Anatolian culture. They are the common point of many different cultures living in Anatolia. They reflect local gastronomy and also socialization spots. This allows them to have an important place in terms of social benefit, by providing economic inputs, supporting employment, supporting local production and helping to preserve the cultural values of the society (Denk, 2023; Elmacioğlu & Seçme, 2023).

1.3. Loyalty

In the literature, loyalty is generally defined as the tendency to maintain continuity toward a business, product, or service, often expressed in the food and beverage industry as increased customer frequency (Dick & Basu, 1994; Reichheld & Schefer, 2000; Şahin & Biçer, 2020). It refers to customers' repeated preference for the same business based on positive perceptions (Skogland & Siguaw, 2004; Rizwan et al., 2014) and is conceptually linked to "regularity". In traditional taverns, the concept of loyalty has been associated with the concept of regular (Ayhan, 2023), where regulars select taverns not only for gastronomy, service, or ambiance but also for the emotional experiences they provide. Over time, this regularity develops into an emotional, cultural, and behavioral attachment that goes beyond the customer-space relationship, creating strong emotional closeness with the tavern, its owner, and employees, and sustaining loyalty even without direct consumption (Upamannu et al., 2015; Halitoğulları & Dinç, 2020).

1.4. Traditional Tavern Culture

Traditional tavern culture, a centuries-old cultural tradition combining food, drink, music, and conversation, emphasizes social interaction and relaxation and is especially common in the Balkans, Middle East, and Mediterranean, adapting uniquely to local societies over time. Türkiye, hosting many civilizations, developed a shared cultural structure, with drinking culture persisting from ancient Turks through the Ottoman Empire to the Republican Era and today, despite periodic bans and religious prohibitions in the predominantly Muslim society. Taverns have been significant sources for literature and cinema, featuring in numerous works of the Republican period. Raki, the culturally symbolic anise-scented drink,

has a 500-year history dating back to the Ottoman era and became popular in İstanbul taverns after the conquest by Mehmet the Conqueror. With this rich cultural background, taverns developed unique rituals, where etiquette, respect, love, and trust are applied at the table. Culturally, taverns have brought together people from diverse backgrounds, fostering interaction and creating a distinctive cultural space within a society where alcohol consumption was religiously restricted (Ögel, 2006; Gülgen, 2010; Zat, 2013; Erdinçli, 2020a; Şimşek, 2021).

2. Research Model and Research Hypotheses

In the research, the effect of traditional tavern culture and traditional taverns on social benefit, loyalty, and adaptation to new generation taverns, with adaptation defined as the endogenous variable and traditional tavern culture as the exogenous variable. Traditional taverns, accepted as part of a city's cultural heritage, preserve customs and rituals while fostering community spirit, solidarity, and economic growth through local food and beverage offerings for both locals and tourists. By creating social benefits, they strengthen loyalty, as individuals who value these benefits tend to remain committed to traditional taverns rather than choosing alternative venues. In this context, the research hypotheses are developed accordingly.

Acehan (2018) emphasized that people interacted with each other by reading poems in the meyhane. In addition to this situation, he stated that it was a place preferred by the intellectual individuals of the period. Yılmaz (2016) emphasizes that taverns are preferred by poets. In this direction, he states the importance given to taverns by the poets of the period who benefited socially and left an impact on the culture of the society with literary works.

Therefore, individuals who are aware and have experience of the social benefits of traditional taverns will increase their loyalty to traditional taverns and will prefer other food and beverage venues less. Particularly they will stay away from experiencing new generation taverns. In this context, H1, H2 and H3 are proposed as follows;

H₁: As traditional tavern culture increases among regulars, the perception of social benefit created by traditional taverns increases.

H₂: As the traditional tavern culture increases among regulars, the perception of loyalty to traditional taverns increases.

H₃: As the perception of social benefit created by traditional taverns increases among regulars, the perception of loyalty to traditional taverns increases.

Harmandar (2020) emphasized from past to present, the understanding of entertainment in tourism has

Adaptation of Traditional Tavern Culture to New Generation Taverns, Loyalty, and the Impact of Social Benefit: The Case of Çanakkale

undergone changes from time to time. With the development of technology, people's interaction with each other is increasing. As a result of these interactions, past entertainment concepts have been forgotten and new ones have been formed instead. Lale and Koca (2023) mentions the change and modernization of entertainment culture over time. In this direction, the research hypothesis 4 was formed as follows.

H₄: While traditional tavern culture increases among regulars, adaptation to new generation taverns decreases.

Perceptions play an important role in individuals' attitudes and behaviors. Perceptions that arise as a result of individuals' interaction with their external environment shape their thoughts, attitudes and behaviors over time (Arkonaç, 2001). For this reason, the events that individuals experience in a conventional order make it difficult for them to have attitudes and behaviors towards a new order. In addition, the individual's ability to adapt to and adopt an innovation occurs when he/she thinks that it benefits him/her (Yeloğlu, 2007). Gültekin & Onsekiz (2005) examined the changing understanding of entertainment in Turkey's Ankara province. They emphasized that the increase in the city population and the political understanding of the period made important changes in the understanding of entertainment. The emergence of a new generation understanding in taverns can be associated with this issue. Under the influence of technology, there are changes in society's understanding of consumption and entertainment. In this direction, hypothesis 5 is formed as follows.

H₅: While the perception of social benefit created by traditional taverns increases among regulars, compliance with new generation taverns decreases.

The concept of regularity becomes prominent in traditional taverns. Regularity occurs as a result of emotional and physical attachment to the place and is associated with loyalty (Ayhan, 2023). Individuals' loyalty to the venue affects their behavioral intentions. In particular, as individuals' loyalty to the venue offering touristic products or services increases, their intention to revisit and recommend to the existing establishment increases (Chi & Qu, 2008; Hernandez-Rojas, Folgado-Fernandez & Palos-Sanchez, 2021). In this context, individuals' high loyalty to traditional taverns may reduce their preferences for new generation taverns and create difficulties in their adaptation. H₆ is proposed as follows.

H₆: While individuals' perception of loyalty to traditional taverns increases, compliance with new generation taverns decreases.

Temurçin & Alaydin (2021) emphasized that in chan-

ges are realized in the spatial preferences of individuals as their age increases. Suggestions were made for elderly tourist groups and it was stated that strategies should be developed for these tourists. Duygun & Koçyiğit (2021) based on research the places preferred by segments of society may differ according to age. It is stated that the types of spaces differ according to the segments of society. The functions of the spaces are shaped according to the structure of the society and their preferences are made according to this shaping. In Sönmez's (2022) master's thesis titled "Places that have lost their gender, an analysis on the transformation of taverns in northern Cyprus", tavern preferences differ according to both gender and age. It is stated that taverns were previously characterized as places preferred more by men. It is emphasized that women also prefer them with modernization. He states that there are old taverns that are generally preferred by middle age and above. He states that the preferences of women and new generation taverns have increased.

H₇: As the age of regulars increases, compliance with new generation taverns decreases.

H₈: While the traditional tavern experience of the regulars increases, the adaptation to the new generation tavern decreases.

Nowadays, traditional taverns have slowly begun leave their place to the new generation taverns. New generation taverns emerged as a result of the dominance of popular culture. However, new generation taverns are entertainment venues where music and dance are at the forefront. In particular, new generation taverns are preferred by younger individuals because of their more modern music and food and beverage offerings. It is known that middle and older age individuals are more likely to prefer traditional taverns because of the atmosphere they are used to (Aydin, 2022; Güzel et al., 2023). The main reason for this can be seen as the fact that young individuals are more open to looking for new products and service offerings with taking risks, and older individuals want to continue to experience traditional products and services without taking risks (Han & Ryu, 2007; Türkmen dağ & Hassan, 2018). Otherwise, it becomes easier for individuals to adopt the product or service depending on their experience with it (Wang et al., 2008). At this point, the high age and experience of individuals who prefer traditional taverns will increase their loyalty to these places and make it difficult for them to adapt to new generation taverns. This case is the main reason for both H₇ and H₈. Eight hypotheses were proposed within the scope of the research. Structural equation modeling of these hypotheses is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Model and Hypotheses

3. Method

3.1. Measuring Tool

In the research, the impact of traditional tavern culture on individuals' social benefit, loyalty and adaptation to new generation taverns created by traditional taverns has been investigated within the framework of individuals' intangible cultural heritage. The effect of social benefit and loyalty to the traditional tavern on adaptation to the new generation taverns was also examined. It was also investigated whether the age and experience of the regulars had an effect on the adaptation to the new generation of taverns. In the literature of the research, no scale that was developed and validated to measure the latent variables of the study was found. Thereupon, before the current research, a qualitative study "Traditional Turkish Tavern Culture and New Generation Taverns within the Scope of Intangible Cultural Heritage¹" and "Traditional Turkish Taverns within the Scope of Intangible Cultural Heritage: Canakkale Example²" was conducted. The statements related to the latent variables were created from interviews, research findings and other studies available in the literature (Eksen, 2000; Öncü et al., 2001; Zat, 2002; Zat, 2013; Koçu, 2015; Erdiñçli, 2020a; Erdiñçli, 2020b; Zat, 2020; Erdiñçli, 2023). The survey was based on a 5-point Likert scale (1 strongly disagree to 5

strongly agree). In this context, a scale consisting of 37 items was developed in the research. The traditional tavern culture dimension of the scale consists of 7 items, the social benefit dimension consists of 10 items, the loyalty to traditional tavern dimension consists of 9 items, and the adaptation to the new generation tavern dimension consists of 11 items.

3.2. Setting and Sample

The research was carried out in Canakkale province. Therefore, the population of the research consists of individuals who live in Canakkale and have tavern experience. A survey was used to obtain the data of the research and the surveys were filled out face to face and online. At the same time, those who regularly visit traditional taverns and tavern staff were asked to send the survey to their acquaintances who are regular patrons in Canakkale via social media platforms. In the research, purposive sampling technique and snowball sampling technique, which are non-probability sampling methods, were preferred. A total of 409 usable surveys were obtained in the research. Therefore, it contains 409 regulars information that is suitable for data analysis. The data for the research were collected between February 2024 and June 2024.

¹Güzel, L., Duran, E. and Hamarat, B. (2023). Somut Olmayan Kültürel Miras Kapsamında Geleneksel Türk Meyhane Kültürü ve Yeni Nesil Meyhaneler. In 7th International West Asia Congress Of Tourism Research (P. 348-369). 08-10 June 2023 Skopje, North Macedonia.

²Can, M., Güzel, L., Hamarat, B., Duran, E. and Gümüşdal, F. (2024). Traditional Turkish Taverns as Intangible Cultural Heritage: The case of Çanakkale. International Tourism Economy Culture Congress (ITEC). 08-10 May 2024 Skopje, North Macedonia.

3.3. Limitations

Since the research was conducted in Çanakkale province, generalizations can only be made from the research findings to the Çanakkale community. Traditional taverns with intangible cultural heritage potential were discussed in the research. The opinions of individuals who do not have knowledge about traditional taverns and new generation tavern culture were not included in the research.

3.4. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling

SmartPLS ready-made software is one of the data analysis tools. Analysis logic is based on PLS-SEM. PLS-SEM, called variance-based structural equation modeling. PLS-SEM analysis methods use the least squares method such as regression as a prediction method. It is based on estimating the relationship coefficients that maximize the R² value of the dependent variable. In other words, it is a method written to minimize the variance of the error terms while maximizing the explained variance of the dependent variable, the latent variable (Duran et al., 2022; Hair et al., 2014).

Testing linearity is another requirement that is looked in the structural model's fit. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value should not exceed three while analysing the multilinear connection between observed variables. However, Smart-PLS recognises that the tolerance value could be greater than 0.20 or the VIF value may be less than 5 for the lack of multicollinearity. These are regarded as problematic linearity levels (Hair et al., 2017; Yıldız, 2020).

The method does not require larger samples as the model becomes more complex and the number of estimated parameters increases, as in covariance-based structural equation modeling. In addition, the method does not require any distribution assumption in structural equation modeling and creates samples from the data set based on the bootstrap technique. It is a non-parametric method that deals with the parameters obtained from each sample (Civelek, 2018).

In order to ensure convergent validity of the partial least squares structural equation model, three basic criteria must be met. First, the standard factor loading of each observed variable belonging to latent variables must be greater than 0.70 and less than 0.90 (Chin, 1998). Secondly, for each construct, Composite Reliability (CR), Cronbach Alpha (CA), convergent validity, and discriminant validity have to be established, with values greater than 0.70 (Hair et al., 2017). Finally, the Average Variance Extracted

(AVE) value for each structure must be higher than 0.50. Additionally, it should be $CR > AVE$ (Gürbüz, 2019; Grima et al., 2021).

Another criterion in testing the structural equation model is discriminant validity. Discriminant validity; is expressed as the separation of a structure/factor from other structures in terms of its properties. Discriminant validity is measured in three ways. In order to ensure discretisation or discriminant validity, the load value of an indicator in one structure must be at least 0.100 units higher than the load value in other structures. The second distinguishing feature is the criterion value developed by Fornell and Larcker (1981). The Fornell-Larcker criterion is the comparison of the square root of the AVE values of the variables with the values in the correlation matrix between the structures. The square root of the AVE value on the diagonal is greater than the correlation values in the row and column it belongs to. The distinctive final model evaluation is checking the HTMT (Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio) coefficients. Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M. and Sarstedt, M (2015), it shows the ratio of the average of the correlations of the variables for all expressions in the research to the geometric averages of the correlations of the same variable. The authors stated that in concepts that are theoretically close to each other, 0.90 should be smaller than 0.85 in other cases.

One of the criteria by which the model is evaluated is the fit criteria. One of the compatibility criteria provided by the SmartPLS ready-made software is SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) and Rms Theta values. Fit criteria show the extent to which the proposed model matches the available data. The SRMR value is between 0-1. While an SRMR value of 0 indicates perfect fit, a value less than 0.80 is considered sufficient (Kline, 2005). The other fit criterion is the Rms Theta value, which measures the closeness of the structural model to the observed data and how close the estimated parameter values are to the observed data. The Rms Theta value must be less than 0.12 (Henseler et al., 2014, Hair et al., 2017).

In PLS-SEM, the predictive power of the model can be calculated with R² and f². R² value gives the explanation ratio of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. Another effect size is f². f² gives the explanation ratio of exogenous variables in the endogenous variable. An effect size of 0.02 and above indicates a low effect, a value of 0.15 and above indicates a medium effect, and a value of 0.35 and above indicates a high level effect (Hair et al., 2017). Another effect coefficient is the predictive power (Blindfolding) value. Prediction power shows the power of the model to predict latent variables and is expressed as the effect size criterion (Yıldız, 2020).

4. Findings

4.1. Descriptive Findings

The research was conducted on 409 regulars. 46.5% of the regulars are women and 53.5% are men. 56.7% of the regulars are married and 43.3% are single regulars. 22.0% of the regulars have a postgraduate education, 52.3% have an undergraduate education. The rate of regulars with associate degree is 13.2%, the rate of regulars with secondary education (High School etc.) is 12.5%. The average age of the regulars was calculated as 44.42 ± 10.879 , 11.2% of them were determined to be 30 years old and under. It was determined that 26.7% of the regulars were

between the ages of 31-40 and 31.5% were between the ages of 41-50. It is estimated that 30.6% of regulars are 51+ years old. The monthly frequency of frequent tavern visits by regulars was calculated as 2.33 ± 1.563 .

Regulars have been going to the tavern for an average of 20.45 ± 10.819 years. While the rate of those who have been going to taverns for ten years or less is 22.5%, 35.5% of them had been going to taverns for 11-20 years. The proportion of regulars who have been going to the tavern for 21-30 years is 29.1%. 13.0% of the regulars visiting the tavern as 31+ years. The results obtained are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics and Frequency Distribution of Regulars

Variable	Characteristic	N	%
Sex	Women	190	46.5
	Men	219	53.5
Marital status	Married	232	56.7
	Single	177	43.3
Education	Postgraduate	90	22.0
	Bachelor degree	214	52.3
	Associate degree	54	13.2
	High School	51	12.5
Age	21-30 years	46	11.2
	31-40 years	109	26.7
	41-50 years	129	31.5
	51+ years	125	30.6
Years going to the tavern	1-10 years	92	22.5
	11-20 years	145	35.5
	21-30 years	119	29.1
	31+ years	53	13.0

4.2. Structural Equation Model Findings

No scale with accepted validity and reliability was found to measure the latent variables of the study. Thereupon, interviews have been conducted with people who were assumed to have a traditional tavern culture, and the interviews of the interviewees were recorded. During the interviews, the themes of 'Traditional Turkish Tavern Concept and Traditional Tavern Culture' were researched and examined in Maxqda ready-made software. Statements were created in four main themes from the interviews and findings of the research. Themes were considered as scales and each scale has been evaluated within itself. The common factor structures of the expressions have been examined with the exploratory Factor Analysis. Principal Components Method was preferred as the method, and Varimax method was preferred for factor rotation. Sample adequacy for

exploratory factor analysis had been examined with the Kaiser-Mayer-Olkin measurement. Whether the correlation matrix used in calculating the factor loading matrix was an identity matrix was calculated using the Bartlett test statistic. Each scale had been examined within itself to determine common factor structures. This is because the research is not a scale development study. In the study where the common factor structures of the "traditional tavern culture" scale were examined, a single factor was found and it was determined that a single factor explained 61.503% of the total variance. It was determined that the common factor structure of the "Loyalty to the traditional tavern" scale was gathered into a single factor. It was determined that this determined factor explained 56.202% of the total variance. Since the factor load of the expressions SB1 and SB2 in the 'social benefit' scale was calculated to be less

Adaptation of Traditional Tavern Culture to New Generation Taverns, Loyalty, and the Impact of Social Benefit: The Case of Çanakkale

than 0.40 in the obtained factor structure, they were removed from the scale and the scale was collected in a single factor and it was determined that it explained 63.895% of the total variance. Finally, the common factor structures of the "adaptation to new generation taverns" scale were examined and it was seen that they were collected in a single factor. The single factor identified explains 68.332% of the total variance. Sampling adequacy was examined with the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure and it was determined that KMO values were between 0.832 and 0.939. Therefore, the samples were found sufficient for factor analysis. Whether the correlation matrices used in calculating the factor structures were identity matrix was examined using Bartlett's Test of Sphericity approach and all factors were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

The research model was created by the obtained factors taking into account. In testing the model, it was tested with the structural equation model, which is based on minimum variance and has a non-parametric approach. SmartPLS 3.3.4 ready-made software was used to test the structural model.

In model testing with SmartPLS, standard factor loadings (Factor Loading) must be greater than 0.70 for convergent validity. In addition, VIF values, which are indicators of multicollinearity, should not be greater than 3 or 5. In the study, the criterion that the VIF value was not greater than 5 was taken into account. In testing the model, the VIF value of the observed variable A3 was determined to be greater than the critical value 5 and was removed from the analysis. No linear multicorrelation was found among other observed variables. The largest VIF value was calculated as 4.667. For convergent validity, factor loadings must be greater than the threshold value of 0.70. In the study, it was determined that there were observed variables with factor loadings less than 0.70. Among these variables, SB1 and SB2 were removed from the scale because their factor loading was less than 0.60 and the AVE value for the latent variable was less than 0.50 which is less than the critical value. These two statements were also determined as items that disrupt the factor in the exploratory factor analysis. Since the AVE value for convergent validity

in all factors was calculated to be greater than the threshold value of 0.50, observed variables with a factor loading of less than 0.70 were not removed from the analysis. Thus, it was decided that convergent validity was achieved.

In the study, internal consistency reliabilities for the structures included in the model were also examined. Cronbach Alpha, Henseler's rho_A and Composite Reliability statistics were examined for internal consistency reliability. Since the internal consistency reliabilities of all structures were determined to be greater than the threshold value of 0.70, the internal consistency reliabilities of the structures were ensured.

Since the AVE value for convergent validity was greater than 0.50 in all structures, it was decided that convergent validity was achieved. The discriminant validity of the structures was decided by looking at the Fornell-Larcker Criterion and HTMT statistics. For the Fornell-Larcker Criterion, the correlation values (square root of the AVE value) of each variable were calculated to be greater than the threshold value of 0.70 and were found to be greater than other correlations in the same row and column. To ensure the discriminant validity of the constructs, the HTMT criterion must also be met. In the study, when the highest HTMT statistic was calculated as $0.856 < 0.900$, the HTMT criterion was also met. In addition, cross loads were examined and no observed variables were found to be loaded on more than one structure. Therefore, discriminant validity of the constructs for the model was ensured in the study.

For the model obtained in the research, the fit values of the model were examined with SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) and Rms Theta values. SRMR statistic was calculated as 0.079 for the fit of the structural model. Another fit statistic is the Rms Theta value, which measures the closeness of the structural model to the observed data and how close the estimated parameter values are to the observed data. In the research, the Rms Theta value was calculated as 0.111, lower than the threshold value of 0.120, and it was decided that the model was an appropriate model. The results obtained are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Critical Values for Adaptation to New Generation Taverns

		E	TTC	L	SB	Age	A
Fornell-Larcker	Traditional tavern experience (E)	1.000					
	Traditional tavern culture (TTC)	0.182	0.784				
	Loyalty to the traditional tavern (L)	0.122	0.555	0.749			
	Social benefit (SB)	0.193	0.768	0.515	0.735		
	Age	0.856	0.188	0.201	0.223	1.000	
	New generation taverns adaptation (A)	-0.361	-0.388	-0.049	-0.253	-0.345	0.823

AVE		1.000	0.615	0.561	0.541	1.000	0.677
Cronbach's Alpha		1.000	0.910	0.888	0.878	1.000	0.947
rho_A		1.000	0.914	0.893	0.890	1.000	0.958
Composite Reliability		1.000	0.927	0.911	0.903	1.000	0.954
HTMT	Traditional tavern experience (E)	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
	Traditional tavern culture (TTC)	0.193	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
	Loyalty to the traditional tavern (L)	0.132	0.598	-----	-----	-----	-----
	Social benefit (SB)	0.204	0.836	0.587	-----	-----	-----
	Age	0.856	0.196	0.210	0.237	-----	-----
	New generation taverns adaptation (A)	0.372	0.399	0.117	0.256	0.357	-----
Greatest VIF		4.667					
SRMR		0.079					
Rms Theta		0.111					

SmartPLS path figure for the effect of traditional tavern culture, loyalty to traditional tavern and social benefit latent variables on adaptation to new generation taverns has been obtained and is given

in figure 2. Since the smallest t value between the latent variables and the observed variables in the path graph was 11.128 > 1.96, all factor loadings were found to be statistically significant.

Figure 2. Path Figure and Relationships Towards Adaptation to New Generation Taverns

According to Figure 2;

- It has been determined that there was a statistically significant $\beta=0.768$ -unit effect in the same direction between the traditional tavern culture and the perception of social benefit created by traditional taverns among the regulars ($t=31.029$ $p=0.000$). According to this determined effect, while the traditional tavern culture increases among the regulars, the perception of social benefit created by traditional taverns increases.
- It has been determined that there was a statistically significant $\beta=0.390$ unit effect in the same direction between the traditional tavern culture and the perception of loyalty to traditional taverns among regulars ($t=4.829$ $p=0.000$). According to this determined effect, as the traditional tavern culture increases, the perception of loyalty to traditional taverns increases among the regulars. Therefore, Hypothesis 2 was supported.
- Therefore, Hypothesis 1 was supported.

Adaptation of Traditional Tavern Culture to New Generation Taverns, Loyalty, and the Impact of Social Benefit: The Case of Çanakkale

- It has been determined that there was a statistically significant $\beta=0.215$ unit effect in the same direction between the perception of social benefit created by traditional taverns and the perception of loyalty to traditional taverns among regulars ($t=2.107$ $p=0.035$). According to this determined effect, the perception of benefit of traditional taverns increases among regulars, while the perception of loyalty to traditional taverns increases. Therefore, Hypothesis 3 was supported.
- It has been determined that there was a statistically significant $\beta=0.555$ unit effect in the opposite direction between the traditional tavern culture and adaptation to new generation taverns among regulars ($t=9.001$ $p=0.000$). According to this determined effect, while the traditional tavern culture increases among the regulars, the adaptation to the new generation taverns decreases. Therefore, Hypothesis 4 was supported.
- It has been determined that there is an effect of $\beta = 0.112$ units between the perception of social benefit created by traditional taverns and adaptation to new generation taverns. This determined effect did not constitute sufficient statistical evidence ($t=1.440$ $p=0.150$). Therefore, Hypothesis 5 was not supported.
- It has been determined that there was a statistically significant $\beta=0.258$ unit effect in the opposite direction between the regulars' perception of loyalty to traditional taverns and adaptation to new generation taverns ($t=3.595$ $p=0.000$). According to this determined effect, while the loyalty of the regulars to the traditional tavern increases, the compliance with the new generation taverns decreases. Therefore, Hypothesis 6 was supported.
- It has been determined that there was a statistically significant reverse effect of $\beta=0.204$ units between the ages of traditional tavern goers and their adaptation to the new generation tavern ($t=2.004$ $p=0.041$). According to this determined effect, as the age of the regulars increases, compliance with the new generation taverns decreases. Therefore, Hypothesis 7 was supported.
- It has been determined that there was a statistically reverse effect of $\beta = 0.157$ units between the traditional tavern goers' traditional tavern experience and their adaptation to the new generation tavern. This determined effect was not found to be statistically significant ($t=1.617$ $p=0.106$). Therefore, Hypothesis 8 was not supported. Hypothesis results, factor loadings and information about the findings for the research model in figure 1 are given in Table 4. In the table, R squares show the explained variance.

Table 4. Hypothesis Results and Factor Loadings

Factors/Structures	Code	Standard loads	t value	R2	Structure reliability			AVE
					CA	rho_A	CR	
Adaptation to new generation taverns (A)	A1	0.851	49.034	0.724	0.947	0.958	0.954	0.677
	A2	0.821	47.828	0.674				
	A4	0.738	29.455	0.545				
	A5	0.907	104.692	0.823				
	A6	0.816	43.990	0.666				
	A7	0.859	48.516	0.738				
	A8	0.847	48.561	0.717				
	A9	0.758	35.059	0.575				
	A10	0.862	62.943	0.743				
	A11	0.752	30.485	0.566				
	Social benefit (SB)	SB3	0.762	23.985	0.581	0.878	0.890	0.903
SB4		0.623	11.411	0.388				
SB5		0.736	25.262	0.542				
SB6		0.737	19.889	0.543				
SB7		0.772	26.568	0.596				
SB8		0.790	24.784	0.624				
SB9		0.616	11.128	0.379				
SB10		0.820	36.672	0.672				

Loyalty to the traditional tavern (L)	L1	0.781	25.488	0.610	0.888	0.893	0.911	0.561
	L2	0.710	22.084	0.504				
	L3	0.736	19.228	0.542				
	L4	0.726	18.650	0.527				
	L5	0.707	15.184	0.500				
	L6	0.778	33.340	0.605				
	L7	0.815	23.909	0.664				
	L8	0.732	17.119	0.536				
Traditional tavern culture (TTC)	TTC1	0.814	28.945	0.663	0.910	0.914	0.927	0.615
	TTC2	0.727	17.631	0.529				
	TTC3	0.710	22.923	0.504				
	TTC4	0.792	22.405	0.627				
	TTC5	0.797	29.158	0.635				
	TTC6	0.806	29.524	0.650				
		0.848	35.216	0.719				
Hypothesis	Standard loads	Standard Error	t-Value	P	Result			
H1: TTC --> SB	0.768	0.025	31.029	0.000	Supported			
H2: TTC --> L	0.390	0.081	4.829	0.000	Supported			
H3: SB --> L	0.215	0.102	2.107	0.035	Supported			
H4: TTC --> A	-0.555	0.062	9.001	0.000	Supported			
H5: SB --> A	0.112	0.078	1.440	0.150	Not supported			
H6: L --> A	-0.258	0.072	3.595	0.000	Supported			
H7: Age --> A	-0.204	0.102	2.007	0.041	Supported			
H8: E --> A	-0.157	0.097	1.617	0.106	Not supported			

The predictive power of the tested model was examined with Adjusted R^2 . R^2 values can be seen in latent variables in the model. According to the regulated R^2 ;

Traditional tavern culture and social benefit variables explain 32.7% of the change in the latent variable of loyalty to traditional taverns. The traditional tavern culture variable explains 59.0% of the change in the social benefit latent variable. It has been determined that 29.4% of the change in the latent variable of adaptation to new generation taverns, the endogenous variable that was tried to be explained in the research, was explained by external variables, age and experience variables.

Effect sizes were measured with f^2 value and the following effect levels were reached.

It has been determined that the effect level of the traditional tavern culture variable on the loyalty to traditional taverns variable was low, with $f^2=0.093$. It has been determined that the effect level of the traditional tavern culture variable on the social benefit variable provided by traditional taverns was high,

with $f^2=1.441$. It has been determined that the effect level of the traditional tavern culture variable on the adaptation to new generation taverns variable was moderate, with $f^2=0.162$. It has been determined that the effect level of the loyalty to the traditional tavern variable on the adaptation to new generation taverns variable was low, with $f^2=0.061$. It has been determined that the effect level of the social benefit variable on the loyalty to traditional taverns variable was low, with $f^2=0.028$.

The predictive powers of the structural model for endogenous variables were measured with Q^2 and the following results were obtained.

It has been determined that the structural model loyalty variable had a medium level of predictive power with $Q^2 = 0.178$. It has been determined that the structural model social benefit variable had a medium level of predictive power with $Q^2 = 0.306$. It has been determined that the structural model had a medium level of predictive power with $Q^2 = 0.188$ in the adaptation variable to new generation taverns. The results obtained are given in Table 5.

Adaptation of Traditional Tavern Culture to New Generation Taverns, Loyalty, and the Impact of Social Benefit: The Case of Çanakkale

Table 5. Effect and Power Statistics For The Tested Model

		Loyalty	Social benefit	Adaptation
Corrected R ²		0.324	0.589	0.286
f ²	Traditional tavern experience			0.009
	Traditional tavern culture	0.093	1.441	0.162
	Loyalty to traditional taverns			0.061
	Social benefit	0.028		0.007
	Age			0.012
Q ²		0.172	0.306	0.188

5. Discussion, Conclusion and Suggestions

5.1. Discussion

Anatolian lands have hosted many civilizations from past to present and are a repository of cultural heritage. The concept of cultural heritage is considered an important factor in the preservation of the Turkish culture (Açıci et al., 2017). Importance should be given to preserving cultural assets, transferring them to future generations, keeping them under historical protection and using them for tourism purposes. Because cultural assets are one of the most important factors that reflect the structure of the society in which they exist. It is possible to consider traditional taverns as one of the most basic elements that reflect the sociological structure and gastronomy of Turkish society. Traditional taverns are places that have survived from past to present and have their own rituals, drinking rules and cultural interactions (Acehan, 2018).

Many taverns were operated during the Ottoman period, and poetry, recitals and literary conversations took place in these taverns. In this respect, it is possible to conclude that events that may benefit the society take place in traditional taverns through cultural interactions. According to Acehan (2018), it is stated that those who prefer taverns generally chat and discuss literary values, and conversations about poetry and literature are held. He also states that people share their knowledge with each other in taverns. Therefore, while the traditional tavern culture is increasing today, as in the past, the social benefit created by traditional taverns is increasing.

Traditional taverns are at the basis of cultural interactions. With the conquest of İstanbul by the Ottoman Empire, Muslims and non-Muslims began to spend time together in taverns. It has been stated that Muslims prefer taverns despite periodic bans (Erdoğanlı, 2023). In Erdoğanlı's (2023) who is described as places where regulars meet the staff and other regulars and where pleasant conversations occur as a ritual. Therefore, regulars feel loyal to the places and experience the tavern culture. Therefore, today,

as in the past, there is a connection between tavern culture and loyalty to the traditional tavern. This result was also reached in the research.

It is seen in the literature that one of the reasons why tavern goers prefer taverns is to socialize (Zat, 2002; Yılmaz, 2005). By the foundation of the Republic, people's socialization opportunities have changed. Places started to play a mediating role in establishing interactions between people and having a good time. Şahin (2021) he states that people have the opportunity to get to know each other better through the interactions they create among themselves. Birer (2018) states that entertainment organizations were organized in taverns by non-Muslims. It was stated that Turks also participated in these entertainment organizations organized by non-Muslims. It is stated that these performances in taverns made important contributions to Turkish classical music. In addition, the fact that Muslims, along with non-Muslims, prefer taverns and that they still continue today reveals that the concept of loyalty is still supported. In line with the information obtained within the scope of the research, it can be said that people show cultural development by interacting with each other in the tavern. Therefore, it can be said that while the social benefit generated by traditional taverns has increased in the past, the perception of loyalty to traditional taverns has increased. A similar result was found in the research and social benefit increased loyalty to the tavern.

The study shows that an increase in traditional tavern culture among regulars enhances their perception of social benefits and loyalty to these taverns. As Eksen (2000), Zat (2002), and Koçu (2015) argued, traditional taverns are social spaces where respectful, sincere, and heartfelt conversations take place, shaped by unique traditions and rituals. This cultural accumulation has been reflected in Turkish literature and songs, highlighting their historical significance. Regulars, therefore, embody traditional tavern culture, etiquette, and rituals, which strengthens both their loyalty and perception of social benefit. Beyond being personal spaces for cultural and experiential sharing, traditional taverns are recognized as part of Turkey's intangible cultural heritage, whose

preservation ensures transmission to future generations. Additionally, by providing local food and beverages to both tourists and locals, these taverns promote social solidarity and contribute to local economic growth.

This study also showcased that cultural depth and tradition are important reasons for preference for both local people and tourists. Therefore, it has been revealed that commitment to tradition and cultural depth resists the superficial post-modern consumption culture. Within this scope the study indicates that increases on traditional tavern culture among the regulars causes decreases on adaptation on new generation taverns. As indicated in the literature (Antil, 1988; Zat, 2002; Wang et al., 2008; Güzel et al., 2023) the touristic destinations and venues like traditional taverns contain a unique culture along with traditions and rituals. However, differences between generations have made changes in the culture of traditional taverns inevitable, and the culture of traditional taverns has disappeared in the so-called new generation taverns. This situation has led to the new generation taverns being seen as places where only alcohol is consumed and far from sincerity, and they have been ignored by individuals who prefer traditional taverns. For this reason, it is revealed that individuals' who have deep knowledge on traditional taverns will create difficulties in adopting and adapting to new generation taverns.

According to the information obtained in the study, it was concluded that those who preferred traditional taverns did not prefer new generation taverns. Traditional tavern goers believe that the taverns they visit are generally places where conversation is predominant and entertainment is not prominent. The taverns that have survived from the Ottoman period to the present day which also vary according to certain characteristics, differ from the new generation taverns that emerged with today's entertainment approach. The main reason why traditional tavern goers prefer taverns is to consume alcohol and chat. However, Harmandar (2020) states that new generation taverns do not match traditional taverns with their loud noises, dances and music. It is stated that there are differences between those who go to taverns that were operated illegally during the Ottoman period and those who prefer taverns called regular taverns (Harmandar, 2020). A similar situation exists between traditional taverns and new generation taverns in today's taverns. This is one of the findings obtained in the research. Therefore, regulars with traditional tavern culture do not adapt to new generation taverns. In addition, regulars who are loyal to the traditional tavern will not adapt to the new generation taverns. In the study, it was found that while loyalty to traditional taverns increased, compliance with new generation taverns decreased.

With the development of technology, people's un-

derstanding of entertainment also changes. People interact more with the opportunities brought by technology. This can increase people's interaction with each other. New generation taverns are places created with a modern consumption approach. Individuals who prefer new generation taverns can visit them mostly to have fun, dance and listen to loud music (Zat, 2020). Traditional taverns can be preferred for chatting, gaining information and literary concerts. It is stated that those who preferred taverns in the Ottoman Empire in the 19th century were well-equipped, cultured, art-loving, well-mannered, easy going, philosophical and influential people. New generation taverns, which are similar to armchair taverns in the past, are generally defined as taverns where people go to drink alcohol (Harmandar, 2020). The Hypothesis established within the scope of the study shows overlap with the information obtained from Harmandar's (2020) study. In addition to this situation, (Acehan, 2018) states that taverns are depicted as an important place in Turkish literature and that literary figures, poets and writers prefer them to refresh themselves, relax, relieve fatigue, get rid of tension and chat. (Acehan, 2018).

Traditional taverns differ conceptually from new generation taverns, serving as spaces where poets and writers historically exchanged ideas and emotions. Consistent with the literature, the study finds that as traditional tavern culture and rituals are maintained, regulars tend to avoid new generation taverns, supporting the hypothesized inverse relationship between loyalty to traditional taverns and adaptation to new generation ones.

The concept of regularity, closely linked to loyalty, reflects the emotional or physical attachment of patrons to a place (Ayhan, 2023). While people from different social classes may frequent the same tavern, their preferences differ based on cultural priorities, meaning traditional tavern regulars are less likely to prefer new generation taverns. Literature highlights that the motivations for visiting traditional versus new generation taverns differ, with historical taverns organizing entertainment in the 17th and 18th centuries to cultivate regular customers (Erdoğanlı, 2020a, 2020b). Similarly, modern new generation taverns adopt this approach to boost consumption and economic gain.

Although new generation taverns have different features from traditional taverns, they are places with economic inputs. They can create a multiplier effect on the economy with their food and drink features. In this sense, there should be a positive relationship between the perception of social benefit and adaptation to new generation taverns. In the study, a relationship was found between social benefit and harmony, but this relationship was not found to be statistically significant.

5.2. Conclusion and Suggestions For Further Studies

Traditional taverns, with their unique cultural heritage rituals, have the potential to take their place among the most important tourism preferences of purposeful and conscious gastronomy tourists. The transfer of the tangible and intangible cultural heritage of traditional taverns to tourism and the provision of sociocultural and socioeconomic benefits within this framework will ensure the development of social awareness, protection and development reflexes for these values. The research results also overlap extensively with social change theory in this context. Therefore;

- The research results show that the development and deepening of the deep cultural rituals, gastronomy and behavioral patterns of traditional taverns will also create positive sociocultural and socioeconomic effects on the local society.
- Similarly, it turns out that increasing consciousness and awareness of the tangible and intangible cultural heritage of traditional taverns increases the level of loyalty to these places. This result shows that destination loyalty regarding the tourism experience will similarly increase.
- The increase in the perception of benefits regarding traditional taverns and their values reveals a social reflex to protect and develop the social and cultural values of these taverns. This situation, like the other results mentioned above, constitutes the main framework of social change theory.
- Every traditional and profound element has an important place in tourism and motivation for participation in tourism. In this context, it becomes clear that the protection of traditional taverns is important in terms of tourism and tourist sustainability.

As a result, the fact that traditional taverns are one of the basic inputs of Anatolian culture is important for our country's tourism because it will play an important role in both ensuring the development of the country's tourism in a sustainable perspective and preserving the social and cultural identity of the destination. In this context, presenting the cultural values that traditional taverns have and reflect to tourism will strengthen social ties and increase awareness of social identity, social loyalty and cultural values.

The research has progressed through traditional taverns in the province of Çanakkale. Within the scope of the research, research can be conducted in places where the number of traditional taverns is higher. Since there are not many studies on traditional taverns, the subject can be examined again from different perspectives. Traditional tavern gastronomy and traditional gastronomic products of Turkish taverns can be examined.

The limitation of researches on traditional taverns in the literature stands out as an important criterion that increases the contribution level of this study to the field and enables it to offer new hypotheses to be tested in the field. At the same time, this is the basic criterion of the originality of the work. It can be a guide for researchers who focus on these concepts.

The fact that there are a limited number of studies in the literature modeling the cause and effect relationship between the variables affecting the patrons' choice of traditional taverns or their adaptation to new generation taverns also reveals the contribution of this study to the literature.

In this regard, the sample can be enlarged and data can be collected from more participants. Tavern rituals in different regions can be investigated. The relationship between cultural differences in the understanding of alcohol consumption and its effects on traditional taverns can be examined and added to the literature. Studies can be conducted on topics such as examining traditional tavern gastronomy, the sustainability of intangible cultural heritage elements, and the place of traditional taverns in society.

References

- Acehan, A. (2018). Yenileşme Dönemi Türk Şiirinde Bir Mekân Olarak Meyhane. *Folklor Akademisi Dergisi*, 1(3), 375-408.
- Açııcı, F. K., Ertaş, Ş., & Sönmez, E. (2017). Sürdürülebilir Turizm: Kültür Turizmi ve Kültürel Miras. *Akademia Disiplinlerarası Bilimsel Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 3(1), 52-66.
- Altun, Ö., & Elidemir, S. N. (2023). Kıbrıs meyhane lezzetlerinin gastronomi turizmi bağlamında incelenmesi. *Sosyal, Beşerî ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 6(3), 410-426.
- Andereck, K. L., Valentine, K. M., Knopf, R. C., and Vogt, C. A. (2005). Residents' Perceptions of Community Tourism Impacts. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 32(4), 1056-1076.
- Antil, J. H. (1988). New Product or Service Adoption: When does it Happen? *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 5(2), 5-16.
- Arkoñaç, A. S. (2001). *Sosyal Psikoloji*. Alfa Yayınları. İstanbul.
- Attanasi, G., Casoria, F., Centorrino, S., & Urso, G. (2013). Cultural Investment, Local Development and Instantaneous Social Capital: A Case Study of a Gathering Festival in the South of Italy. *The Journal of Socio-Economics*, 47, 228-247.
- Ay, Ş., & Şahin, K., (2014). Eski Yakındoğu'da Yemek Simgeselliği Üzerine Bir Değerlendirme. *Tarihin Peşinde Uluslararası Tarih ve Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, Vol.6, No.12, 331-358.
- Aydın, H. (2022). *Yeni Nesil Meyhaneler*. Meyhane İhtisas Kitabı, Editörler: Erdir Zat, A. Nilhan Aras, Engin Öncüoğlu, Onur Kutluoğlu, Umut Şumnu, Selin Özavcı, IWSA ve Murat Meriç. (Anason İşleri Kitapları) Overteam Yayınları: İstanbul, pp. 75-80.
- Ayhan, D. (2023). Müdavim: Mekân Aidiyetinin Tipleşmiş Hali. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, (52), 386-396.
- Besculides, A., Lee, M. E., & McCormick, P. J. (2002). Residents' Perceptions of the Cultural Benefits of Tourism. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 29(2), 303-319.
- Birer, M. (2018). Osmanlı Eğlence Müziği Geleneklerinde Sosyo-Kültürel Etkileşimler. *Ahenk Müzikoloji Dergisi*, (3), 66-83.
- Can, M., Güzel, L., Hamarat, B., Duran, E., & Gümüşdal, F. (2024). Traditional Turkish Taverns as Intangible Cultural Heritage: The case of Çanakkale. *International Tourism Economy Culture Congress (ITEC)*. 08-10 May 2024 Skopje, North Macedonia.

- Chi, C. G. Q., & Qu, H. (2008). Examining The Structural Relationships of Destination Image, Tourist Satisfaction and Destination Loyalty: An Integrated Approach. *Tourism Management*, 29(4), 624-636.
- Chin, W. W. (1998). The Partial Least Squares Approach for Structural Equation Modeling. In *Methodology for Business and Management. Modern Methods for Business Research*, G. A. Marcoulides (Eds). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers: Mahwah, pp. 295-336.
- Ciğerim, N. (2001). Batı ve Türk Mutfağının Gelişimi, Etkileşimi ve Yiyecek-İçecek Hizmetlerinde Türk Mutfağının Yerine Bir Bakış. *Türk Mutfak Kültürü Üzerine Araştırmalar*, 28, 49-61.
- Civelek, M.E. (2018). Yapısal Eşitlik Modellemesi Metodolojisi. Beta Basım Yayın Dağıtım: İstanbul.
- Çapraz, E. (2018). Aşık Tarzi Şiir Geleneğinin Teşekkülüne Dair Değerlendirmelere Bir Ek: Meyhaneler. *Türkbilig*, (35), 233-244.
- Demiral, G. N., & Özel, Ç. H. (2016). Restoran Yöneticilerinin Fiziksel Kanıtların Kullanımına Yönelik Bakış Açılarının Belirlenmesi: Eskişehir Örneği. *Manisa Celal Bayar Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 14(4), 191-230.
- Deniz, T. (2024). Kültürel Miras Yönetimi Kapsamında Gastronomi Turizmi. *Safran Kültür ve Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 7(1), 18-28.
- Denk, E. (2023). Erzurum'da Gastronomi Turizminin Toplum Üzerindeki Etkisi: Ekonomik Fırsatlar, Çevresel Endişeler ve Sosyo-Kültürel Zenginlik. *Socrates Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Studies*, 9(34).
- Dick, A. S., & Basu, K. (1994). Customer Loyalty: Toward An Integrated Conceptual Framework. *Journal of The Academy Of Marketing Science*, 22, 99-113.
- Duman, O., Ercan, S., & Yaprak, B. (2021). Festival Katılımcısı İşletmelerin Algılanan Toplumsal Fayda, Algılanan Toplumsal Maliyet ve Katılım Motivasyonlarının Festival Memnuniyeti ve Sadakati Üzerindeki Etkisi. *OPUS International Journal of Society Researches*, 17(35), 2125-2154.
- Duran, E., Hamarat, B. & Özmen, R. (2022). Yiyecekte Yenilik Korkusunun Sosyo-Kültürel Uyum ve Mesleki Tatmin Üzerine Etkisi: Turizm Lisans Öğrencileri Örneği. *Journal of Humanities and Tourism Research*, 12(3), 631-644.
- Duygun, E., & Koçyiğit, R. G. (2021). Tarihi Kent Merkezlerinde Tüketim Mekânlarının Dönüşümü: Yeldeğirmeni Mahallesi Örneği. *Tasarım+ Kuram Journal*, 17(33), 18.
- Eksen, İ. (2000). Dengeli Demlenme ve Rakı Mezeleri. Sel Yayıncılık: İstanbul.
- Elmacioğlu, N., & Seçme, G. (2023). Gastronomi ve Kent Pazarlamasının Kayseri Örneğinde İncelenmesi. *Uluslararası Anadolu Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 7(2), 432-449.
- Erdem, Ö., Mızrak, M., & Kemer, A. K. (2018). Yöresel Yemeklerin Bölge Restoranlarında Kullanılma Durumu: Mengen Örneği. *Uluslararası Türk Dünyası Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 3(1), 44-61.
- Erdoğan, İ. (2020a). İstanbul Meyhanelerinde Sıra Dışı Eğlenceler: 17. Yüzyıldan 20. Yüzyıla Müzik, Raks ve Cinsellik. *Tarih İncelemeleri Dergisi*, 35(1), 101-132.
- Erdoğan, İ. (2020b). Sarhoşluktan Keyif Haline: Osmanlı İstanbul'unda İçki İçme ve Meyhane Âdâbı. *OTAM Ankara Üniversitesi Osmanlı Tarihi Araştırma ve Uygulama Merkezi Dergisi*, (47), 21-44.
- Erdoğan, İ. (2023). 16. Yüzyıldan 20. Yüzyıla İstanbul Meyhane Alemlerine Eşlik Eden Mezeler ve Yiyecekler. *Tarih Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 42(73), 151-180.
- Eryer, A. (2024). Sağlık Turizminin Ekonomik Boyutu: Türkiye Üzerine Bir Değerlendirme. *Journal of Economics and Research*, 5(1), 63-80.
- Fornell, C. & Larcker, D.F. (1981). Evaluating Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39-50.
- Grima, S., Hamarat, B., Özen, E., Girlando, A., & Dalli-Gonzi, R. (2021). The Relationship between Risk Perception and Risk Definition and Risk-Addressing Behaviour during the Early COVID-19 Stages. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(6), 272-297.
- Güler, S. (2010). Türk Mutfak Kültürü ve Yeme İçme Alışkanlıkları. *Dumlupınar Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 26(1), 24-30.
- Gülgen, J. (2010). Bir İstanbul Tutkunu: Reşad Ekrem Koçu. *Türkiye Araştırmaları Literatür Dergisi*, (16), 691-700.
- Gültekin, N., & Onsekiz, D. (2005). Ankara Kentinde Eğlence Mekânlarının Oluşumu ve Yer Seçimi. *Gazi Üniversitesi Mühendislik Mimarlık Fakültesi Dergisi*, 20(1).
- Gürbüz, S. (2019). AMOS ile Yapısal Eşitlik Modellemesi. Seçkin Kitabevi: Ankara.
- Güzel L., Duran E., & Hamarat B. (2023). Somut Olmayan Kültürel Miras Kapsamında Geleneksel Türk Meyhane Kültürü ve Yeni Nesil Meyhaneler. In *7th International West Asia Congress Of Tourism Research* (pp. 348-369). 08-10 June 2023 Skopje, North Macedonia. www.iwact.org/uploads/tam-metin-kitabi.pdf
- Hair, J.F., Hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C.M., & Sarstedt, M. (2014). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Sage Publication: Los Angeles.
- Hair, J.F., Hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C.M., & Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Second Edition, Sage Publication: Los Angeles.
- Halitoğulları, H., & Dinç, N. T. (2020). Marka aşkı, marka sadakati ve ağızdan ağıza pazarlama ilişkisi: THY örneği. *Türk Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 4(4), 3649-3667.
- Han, H., & Ryu, K. (2007). Moderating Role of Personal Characteristics in Forming Restaurant Customers' Behavioral Intentions: An Upscale Restaurant Setting. *Journal of Hospitality and Leisure Marketing*, 15(4), 25-54.
- Harmandar, S. (2020). 19. Yüzyılda İstanbul'da Değişen Eğlence Anlayışı ve Yeni Eğlence Mekânları. *ETÜT Dergisi*, 1(1), 114-117.
- Henseler, J., Dijkstra, T. K., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., Diamantopoulos, A., & Straub, D. W., Ketchen, D. J., Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M. & Calantone, R. J. (2014). Common Beliefs and Reality about PLS: Comments on Rönkkö and Evermann (2013). *Organizational Research Methods*, 17(2): 182-209.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A New Criterion for Assessing Discriminant Validity in Variance-Based Structural Equation Modelling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43, 115-135
- Hernandez-Rojas, R. D., Folgado-Fernandez, J. A., & Palos-Sanchez, P. R. (2021). Influence of The Sestaurant Brand and Gastronomy on Tourist Loyalty. A Study in Córdoba (Spain). *International Journal of Gastronomy and Food Science*, 23, 100305.
- Işık, S. (2018) Locke'un Siyasal Zoolojisi: Yasa, Hayvan ve Egemen. *Liberal Düşünce Dergisi*, 23(91-92), 143-162.
- Kayran, M. F., & Atçı, D. (2024). Geçmişten günümüze gastronomi akımlarının toplumsal değişimler açısından değerlendirilmesi. *Toros University Journal of Food Nutrition and Gastronomy*, 3(1), 69-81.
- Kline, R.B. (2005). *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modelling*. Guilford Press: New York.
- Koçu, R. E. (2015). Eski İstanbul'da Meyhaneler ve Meyhane Köçekleri. İstanbul: Doğan Kitapçılık.
- Kozak, N., Akoğlan Kozak, M. ve Kozak, M. (2013). Genel Turizm İlkeler-Kavramlar (14. Baskı). Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık.
- Köşker, H. (2024). Turizmin Ekonomik, Çevresel ve Sosyo-Kültürel Etkileri. *Turizm Ekonomisi*, 53.
- Lale, B., & Koca, D. (2023). Modern İdeolojinin Mekânsal Oluşumu: 1923-60 Yılları Arası Ankara Gazinoları. *Tasarım Kuram* 2023;19(39):334-350 doi: 10.59215/tasarimkuram.397.
- Mankan, E., & Özçelik, A. Ö. (2019). Yabancı Turistlerin Türk Mutfağındaki Et Yemeklerine İlişkin Görüşleri. *Kesit Akademi Dergisi*, (6), 164-177.
- Maviş, F. (2008). Endüstriyel Yiyecek Üretimi. Detay Yayıncılık: Ankara.
- Ögel, K. (2006). Türkiye'de Alkol Kültürü. https://www.ogelk.net/Dosyadepo/alkol_kulturu_kultegin_ogel.

Adaptation of Traditional Tavern Culture to New Generation Taverns, Loyalty, and the Impact of Social Benefit: The Case of Çanakkale

pdf. Access Date: 20.07.2024.

Öncü, F., Ögel, K., & Çakmak, D. (2001). Alkol Kültürü-1: Tarihsel Süreç ve Meyhane Kültürü. *Bağımlılık Dergisi*, 2(3), 133-138.

Öztekın, Ö. (2005). Cumhuriyet Dönemi Türk Eğlence Kültürü. Akçağ Yayınları: Ankara.

Pine, J. B. and Gilmore, J. H. (1999). *The Experience Economy*. Harvard Business School Press: Boston.

Reichheld, F. F., & Scheffer, P. (2000). E-Loyalty: Your Secret Weapon on The Web. *Harvard Business Review*, 78(4), 105-113.

Rizwan, M., Javed, P. A., Aslam, J., Khan, R., & Bibi, H. (2014). The Relationship of Brand Commitment, Brand Credibility, Perceived Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Brand Loyalty: an Empirical Study on Stylo Shoes. *Journal of Sociological Research*, 5(1), 377-404.

Seylan, A., & Güney, E. (2014). Yeni Medya-İdeoloji İlişkisinde, Küresel Görsel Kültür ve Genç Kitle. Gençlik ve Kültürel Mirasımız Uluslararası Kongre, 16-18 Mayıs 2014. S.29-34 Samsun/Türkiye.

Sezen, İ., & Külekçi, E. A. (2020). Kentsel kimlik bileşenleri ve kış turizmi ilişkisi: Erzurum kenti örneđi. Atatürk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi, 24(4), 1799-1810.

Skogland, I., & Siguaw, J. A. (2004). Are Your Satisfied Customers Loyal? *Cornell Hotel and Restaurant Administration Quarterly*, 45(3), 221-234.

Sormaz, Ü., & Kaya, Ş. (2019). Yiyecek İçecek İşletmelerinde Yöresel Mutfak Uygulamaları: Gaziantep Örneđi. *Gastroia: Journal of Gastronomy and Travel Research*, 3(2), 304-323.

Sönmez, M. G. (2022). Cinsiyetini Kaybeden Mekânlar Kuzey Kıbrıs'ta Meyhanelerin Dönüşümü Üzerine Bir Analiz, Yayınlanmamış Yüksek lisans Tezi, Dođu Akdeniz Üniversitesi Lisansüstü Eğitim, Öğretim ve Araştırma Enstitüsü, Gazimağusa, Kuzey Kıbrıs.

Şahin, B., & Biçer, Ö. (2020). Turistik Tüketicilerde Marka Aşkı ve Marka Sadakati: Otel Müşterileri Örneđi. *Turizm Akademik Dergisi*, 7(1), 133-147.

Şahin, E., & Yazıcıođlu, İ. (2020). Restoran aydınlatmasının menüden yemek seçimine etkisi. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Education Research*, 6(1), 54-66.

Şahin, G. (2021). Cumhuriyet Dönemi Çanakkale'sinde Gündelik Yaşamın Belirleyicisi Olarak Eğlence Mekanları (1923-1973). *Kültür Araştırmaları Dergisi*, (11), 29-48.

Şahin, K. (2011). Kültürel Yozlaşmaya Neden Olan Bir Unsur Olarak Televizyon. *Kırıkkale Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 1(1), 243-277.

Şimşek, A. (2021). Rakı ve Türk Rakı Sofrasındaki Yemek Kültürü. *Erzurum Teknik Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, (12), 76-95.

Tarınç, A., & Özbek, Ö. (2022). Teknolojinin Mutfaka Yansımaları: Aşçı Robotlar Üzerine R Programı. *Gastronomi, Konaklama ve Seyahat Dergisi (Online)*, 5(1), 406 – 416.

Temurçin, K., & Alaydın, N. N. (2021). Yaşlı Turistlerin Mekânsal Tercihleri. *Türkuaz Uluslararası Türk Dünyası Bilimsel Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 2(2), 145-164.

Türkmendağ, T., & Hassan, A. (2018). Müşteri Sadakati Oluşturmada Algılanan Deđerin Etkisi: Bir Çağ Kebap Restoranı Örneđi. *MANAS Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 7(3), 747-775.

Upamannyu, N. K., Bhakar, S. S., & Gupta, M. (2015). Effect of corporate image on brand trust and brand affect. *International Journal of Applied Science-Research and Review*, 2(1), 20-33.

Uygur, S.M., & Baykan, E. (2007). Kültür Turizmi ve Turizmin Kültürel Varlıklar Üzerindeki Etkileri. *Ticaret ve Turizm Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, (2), 30-49.

Üçer, M., & Pekşen, F. (2001). Divriğ'i'de Mutfak Kültürü: Yemekler, Gelenekler, İnançlar, Atasözleri. Sivas Hizmet Vakfı: Sivas.

Wang, Q., Dacko, S., & Gad, M. (2008). Factors Influencing Consumers' Evaluation and Adoption Intention of Really-New Products or Services: Prior Knowledge, Innovativeness and Timing of Product Evaluation. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 35, 416-422.

Yalap, H. (2017). Klasik Türk Edebiyatı Işığında Edebiyat ve Kül-

tür Tarihimizde Kahve ve Kahvehaneler. *İnsan ve Toplum Bilimleri Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 6(3), 1907-1930.

Yelođlu, H. O. (2007). Örgüt, Birey, Grup Bağlamında Yenilik ve Yaratıcılık Tartışmaları. *Ege Academic Review*, 7(1), 133-152.

Yenici, M. (2020). Toplumsal Bellek Kaydı Olarak Ara Güler'in Meyhane Fotoğrafları. *Art-Sanat Dergisi*, (14), 557-577.

Yıldız, E. (2020). Yapısal Eşitlik Modellemesi. Seçkin Yayıncılık, I. Baskı, Ankara.

Yıldız, E., & Davutođlu, N. A. (2020). Turizm 4.0'dan Gastronomi 4.0'a Giden Yolda: Geleceğin Restoranları ve Yönetimi. *Akademik Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 8(109), 301-318.

Yılmaz, F. (2005). Boş Vaktiniz Var mı? veya 16. yüzyılda Anadolu'da Şarap, Eğlence ve Suç. *Tarih ve Toplum: Yeni Yaklaşımlar*, 1, 11-49.

Yılmaz, T. (2016). Hüsrev Hatemi'nin "Dağıtmış Gazel" Şiirinde Metinlerarasılık Bağlamında Modern Hayat Eleştirisi. *Yeni Türk Edebiyatı: Hakemli Altı Aylık İnceleme Dergisi*, (14), 139-162.

Yolal, M. (2017). Türkiye'nin Etkinlik Turizmi Potansiyelinin Deđerlendirilmesi. *Çatalhöyük Uluslararası Turizm ve Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, (2), 35-51.

Yolal, M., Gursoy, D., Uysal, M., Kim, H. L., & Karacaođlu, S. (2016). Impacts of Festivals and Events on Residents' Well-being. *Annals of tourism research*, 61, 1-18.

Zat, E. (2020). Meyhane. <https://turkiyeturizmansiklopedisi.com/meyhane> Access Date: 24.07.2024.

Zat, E. (2013). Rakı Her Dem Yeni, Her Daim Kalender: Rakı Her Dem Yeni, Her Daim Kalender. Overteam Yayınları: İstanbul.

Zat, V. (2002). Eski İstanbul Meyhaneleri. İletişim Yayıncılık: İstanbul.

Zhuang, X., Yao, Y., & Li, J. (2019). Sociocultural Impacts of Tourism on Residents of World Cultural Heritage Sites in China. *Sustainability*, 11(3), 840.